

Benign routes for the syntheses of polydentate Schiff base and their lanthanide complexes

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Abstract : Tris-imine septadentate Schiff base ligand has conveniently made in high yield (~95% or more), when tris(2-aminoethyl)amine condensed with salicylaldehyde using 1 : 3 molar ratio under solvent free conditions. Lanthanide complexes have also synthesised by a unique procedure layering ethanolic solution of the ligand with that of lanthanide salts in water. Characterisation was done using elemental analysis, spectroscopic, magnetic and single crystal X-ray crystallographic studies. Thus, the procedures provide a simple, high yield and green synthetic pathways for the preparation of polydentate ligand and corresponding important lanthanide coordination compounds.

Keywords : Ln^{III} complexes, tripodal ligand, benign synthetic route, spectral and magnetic properties, septacoordination.

Introduction

The demands for more benign synthetic processes continue to increase greater and greater attention has been focused on the development of new and improved synthetic methods. One major topic of interest is to develop solvent free synthetic routes or use non-hazardous or at least less hazardous chemicals as well as solvents¹. Schiff base compounds are widely studied and used, attracting wide range of applications in organic synthesis and metal ion complexation²⁻⁶. The conventional syntheses of such compounds are still very common along with modern synthetic approaches³.

Moreover, the lanthanide compounds have wide spread application as fluorescent probes in biological systems⁷, magnetic resonance imaging and as contrast agents in clinical NMR images⁸. The application of these complexes as magnetic resonance contrasting agents has led to the syntheses of a number of lanthanide(III) complexes with heptadentate tripodal Schiff base ligand⁹⁻¹⁷, and in most cases the coordination number of the Ln^{III} ion is greater than seven. In the present study, water and minimum amount of ethanol used as reaction medium. Polydentate ligand has been synthesized by a solvent free method condensing tris(2-aminoethyl)amine with salicylaldehyde using the mole ratio 1 : 3. While the traditional procedure gave a yield of ~85%¹⁸, the yield by the present

method is ~95% or more. The ligand on reaction with the lanthanide(III) nitrate salt produced heptacoordinated neutral complexes with N₄O₃ as donor sites. The reactions have been performed without using any of the toxic solvents. Crystal structure, room temperature magnetic moment and the luminescent properties of these Ln^{III} complexes (Ln^{III} = Gd, 1; Tb, 2; Dy, 3 and Ho, 4) with the Schiff base ligand H₃L is also reported.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The heptadentate Schiff base ligand (H₃L) was prepared by a solvent free neat reaction method in which the salicylaldehyde was added to the tris(2-aminoethyl)amine slowly and with constant stirring (Scheme 1). The mixture was cooled and a yellow shiny compound was obtained. It was washed with cold ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. By this route one can get higher yield (about 95% or more) compared to traditional methods (yield : about 85%)¹⁸ and avoid the use of toxic solvent which otherwise remains as a waste and pollutes the environment. An ethanolic solution of H₃L was slowly layered with an aqueous solution of Ln(NO₃)₃.xH₂O in a single tube. The setup was kept undisturbed. After two days yellow crystalline compound was obtained in a reasonably high yield (about 80%).

Scheme 1. Synthetic route to Schiff base ligand and lanthanide complexes.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of these complexes involve only a redistribution of electrons within the $4f$ orbitals ($f-f$ transitions) which are orbitally-forbidden by the selection rules. As a result colours of trivalent lanthanide compounds are usually not very intense. Crystal/ligand field effects in lanthanide $4f$ orbitals are virtually insignificant as $4f$ electrons are well shielded from external charge by $5s^2$ and $5p^6$ shells. The complexes 1–4 exhibit intense emission peaks at around 466 nm and 396 nm. The absorption energy of all the four complexes 1–4 in methanol solution is similar ($\lambda_{\max} \sim 350$ nm) and is due to intra ligand fluorescence ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition). The absorption wavelength, emission wavelength, $\log \epsilon$ and intensity are given in Table 1.

Table 1. The absorption wavelength and $\log \epsilon$ of $\text{Ln}^{\text{III}}\text{L}$

Compd.	Absorption (nm) ($\log \epsilon$)	Excitation (nm)
[GdL], 1	353 (7.98)	350
[TbL], 2	353 (8.17)	350
[DyL], 3	352 (7.96)	350
[HoL], 4	352 (8.09)	350

Magnetic study :

The magnetic properties of the lanthanides have both spin and orbital contributions in contrast “spin-only” of d -transition metals. Spin orbit coupling constants are typically large (*ca.* 1000 cm^{-1}) whereas ligand field effects are very small ($\sim 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The room temperature magnetic moment of these complexes have been calculated using the following formula¹⁹.

$$\mu = g [J(J + 1)]^{1/2} \text{ (B.M.)}$$

$$g = 1 + \{S(S + 1) - L(L + 1) + J(J + 1)\} / 2J(J + 1)$$

For all the complexes experimentally found magnetic moment values are in good agreement with that of the calculated values. The magnetic moment (B.M.) values in polycrystalline form for all the complexes are found to be 8.06, 9.43, 10.58 and 10.46 respectively for [GdL] (1), [TbL] (2), [DyL] (3) and [HoL] (4). These values are very close agreement with that of calculated magnetic moments corresponding to $4f^7$, $4f^8$, $4f^9$ and $4f^{10}$ electronic configuration.

Description of the crystal structures :

The ORTEP drawing of the complexes $[\text{Gd}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]$ (1), $[\text{Tb}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]$ (2), $[\text{Dy}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]$ (3) and $[\text{Ho}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]$ (4) are shown respectively in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4 and the selected bond distances and angles are listed in Tables 2 and 3. All the synthesized lanthanide complexes are found to be septa coordinated and have distorted pentagonal bipyramidal geometry. For the Gd complex, the metal-tripodal nitrogen (N1) distance is 2.747(3) Å. Metal-phenolate oxygen (O1) distance is 2.2335(14) Å while the metal-amine (N2) bond distance is 2.5119(16) Å. The O(1)-Gd-O(1)#1 bond angle is 95.55(5)°. O(1)-Gd-N(2) bond angle is 72.93(5)° whereas N(2)-M-O(1)#1 bond angle is 86.82(5)° and N(2)-M-O(1)#2 bond angle is 168.43(5)°. The N(2)-Gd-N(2)#1 bond angle is 104.68(4)°. O(1)-Gd-N(1) bond angle is 121.23(4)° whereas N(2)-Gd-N(1) bond angle is 66.08(4)°. The geometry is actually highly distorted pentagonal bipyramidal as evident from the angle N(2)-M-O(1)#2 considered to be trans is actually 168.43(5)° instead of 180°. The other angles in equatorial plane ranges from 66.08(4)° to 121.23(4)°. The structures of other lanthanide complexes (i.e. Tb, Dy and Ho) are very similar to the

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot (50% thermal ellipsoid) with atom numbering scheme for [Gd^{III}L] (1) For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot (50% thermal ellipsoid) with atom numbering scheme for [Tb^{III}L] (2) For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown

Fig. 3. ORTEP plot (50% thermal ellipsoid) with atom numbering scheme for [Dy^{III}L] (3). For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown.

Fig. 4. ORTEP plot (50% thermal ellipsoid) with atom numbering scheme for [Ho^{III}L] (4). For clarity the hydrogen atoms are not shown.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) for the complexes Ln^{III}L

Bond distance (Å)	Ln ^{III} = Gd	Ln ^{III} = Tb	Ln ^{III} = Dy	Ln ^{III} = Ho
M-O(1)	2.2335(14)	2.222(3)	2.210(3)	2.1985(18)
M-N(1)	2.747(3)	2.731(7)	2.716(5)	2.708(5)
M-N(2)	2.5119(16)	2.497(4)	2.479(4)	2.468(2)

Table 3. Selected bond angles (°) for the complexes Ln^{III}L

Bond angles (°)	Ln ^{III} = Gd	Ln ^{III} = Tb	Ln ^{III} = Dy	Ln ^{III} = Ho
O(1)-M-O(1)#1	95.55(5)	95.84(10)	95.48(10)	94.88(7)
O(1)-M-N(1)	121.23(4)	121.01(7)	121.29(6)	121.73(4)
O(1)-M-N(2)	72.93(5)	73.27(11)	73.65(10)	74.04(6)
N(2)-M-N(1)	66.08(4)	66.18(7)	66.30(7)	66.51(4)
N(2)-M-N(2)#1	104.68(4)	104.79(13)	104.93(12)	105.18(7)
N(2)-M-O(1)#1	86.82(5)	86.00(12)	85.73(11)	85.57(7)
N(2)-M-O(1)#2	168.43(5)	169.10(10)	169.13(9)	168.90(6)

gadolinium complex. This is interesting to observe that the metal-tripodal nitrogen bond distances decreases steadily from Gd 2.747 (Å) to Ho 2.708 (Å) through Tb 2.731 (Å) and Dy 2.716 (Å). This decrease in bond distance is in good agreement with lanthanide contraction. It is interesting to observe that the septadentate ligand does not coordinate through the tripodal nitrogen in case mononuclear 3d and 4d¹⁸ series of metal complexes which is in contrary to the 4f-metal complexes. The mononuclear complex of manganese with 5-chloro derivative of the septadentate ligand has Mn-N(1) distance 3.245(4) (Å), while ruthenium complex with the same unsubstituted ligand has Ru-N(1) distance 3.545(12) (Å)¹⁸. This large metal-nitrogen distance is evidence enough that they are not bonded. But for the 4f metals the metal-tripodal nitrogen distance varies between 2.747(3) (Å) to 2.708(5) (Å) for the four metals under consideration hence proving that the tripodal nitrogen is bonded in this case (*vide supra*).

Experimental

Tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, salicylaldehyde and metal salts were obtained from Lancaster and Aldrich Chemical Company and were used as received. All other solvents and chemicals were of analytical grade.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed (at IACS, Kolkata) using a Perkin-Elmer

2400II elemental analyzer. IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded on (KBr pellets) at 298 K using a Shimadzu Model 8400 S spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at 298 K using a magnetometer (Sherwood Scientific Model MK1). Pascal's constants were utilized to estimate diamagnetic correction; this value was subtracted from the experimental susceptibility data to give molar magnetic susceptibility (χ_M).

Synthesis of ligand and complexes :

The heptadentate ligand (H₃L) was prepared by a solvent free neat reaction method. Tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (0.73 g, 5 mmol) was taken in a round bottom flask. To this salicylaldehyde (1.83 g, 15 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring. The mixture was cooled by ice cold water. A yellow shiny compound was obtained. It was washed with cold ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield : 2.18 g, ~95%. Calcd. for C₂₇H₃₀N₄O₃ : C, 70.71; H, 6.59; N, 12.21%. Found : C, 70.70; H, 6.58; N, 12.20%. The procedure was found to be more superior than the previously reported method in which the yield of the ligand was ~85%^{17,18}.

Preparation of [Gd^{III}L] (1) :

The aqueous solution of Gd(NO₃)₃.6H₂O was taken in 1 ml water (0.113 g, 0.25 mmol) in a single test tube and was slowly layered with a solution of ligand H₃L (0.114 g, 0.25 mmol) in 5 ml ethanol. The setup was kept undisturbed. After two days yellow prismatic crystalline compound of (1) was obtained. Yield : 0.119 g, ~78%. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₇N₄O₃Gd : C, 52.92; H, 4.44; N, 9.14%. Found : C, 52.79; H, 4.71; N, 9.05%; IR (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) : ν (C=N) band are at 1649 cm⁻¹ 4-6.

Preparation of [Tb^{III}L] (2) :

This compound was synthesized following the same procedure as illustrated above for 1 except that Gd(NO₃)₃.6H₂O was replaced by equimolar quantity of Tb(NO₃)₃.5H₂O. Yield : 0.117 g, ~76%. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₇N₄O₃Tb : C, 52.77; H, 4.43; N, 9.12%. Found : C, 52.69; H, 4.31; N, 9.04%; IR (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) : ν (C=N) band are at 1647 cm⁻¹ 4-6.

Preparation of [Dy^{III}L] (3) :

This compound was synthesized following the same procedure as illustrated above for 1 except that Gd(NO₃)₃.

6H₂O was replaced by equimolar quantity of Dy(NO₃)₃. 5H₂O. Yield : 0.123 g, ~80%. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₇N₄O₃Dy : C, 52.47; H, 4.33; N, 9.06%. Found : C, 52.39; H, 4.25; N, 9.01%; IR (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) : ν(C=N) band are at 1649 cm⁻¹ 4–6.

Preparation of [Ho^{III}L] (4) :

This compound was synthesized following the same procedure as illustrated above for **1** except that Gd(NO₃)₃.6H₂O was replaced by equimolar quantity of Ho(NO₃)₃.5H₂O. Yield : 0.11 g, ~73%. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₇N₄O₃Ho : C, 52.26; H, 4.38; N, 9.03%. Found : C, 52.24; H, 4.35; N, 9.00%; IR (KBr disc, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) : ν(C=N) band are at 1650 cm⁻¹ 4–6.

Crystallographic data :

The X-ray diffraction data were collected at 296 K with Mo Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å) using a Bruker Nonius SMART CCD diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromator. SMART software was used for data collection and also for indexing the reflections and determining the unit cell parameters; the collected data were integrated using saint software. The structures were solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares calculations using SHELXTL²⁰ software. All the non-H atoms were refined in the anisotropic approximation. The relevant crystallographic data for all four compounds are given in Table 4.

Table 4. The crystal data and data collection summary for the complexes **1** to **4**

	1	2	3	4
Empirical formula	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₃ Gd	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₃ Tb	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₃ Dy	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₃ Ho
Formula weight	612.78	614.46	618.03	620.46
Crystal system	Trigonal	Trigonal	Trigonal	Trigonal
Space group	<i>P</i> -3 <i>cl</i>	<i>P</i> -3 <i>cl</i>	<i>P</i> -3 <i>cl</i>	<i>P</i> -3 <i>cl</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.0128(8)	13.0030(3)	12.9832(3)	12.9593(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.0128(8)	13.0030(3)	12.9832(3)	12.9593(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.3300(14)	16.3008(9)	16.3004(8)	16.3183(9)
α (°)	90	90	90	90
β (°)	90	90	90	90
γ (°)	120	120	120	120
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2394.7(3)	2386.86(15)	2379.54(14)	2373.39(15)
<i>Z</i>	4	4	4	4
<i>D</i> _{calcd.} (g cm ⁻³)	1.700	1.710	1.725	1.736
<i>F</i> (000)	1220	1224	1228	1232
Crystal size (mm)	0.48 × 0.39 × 0.16	0.51 × 0.33 × 0.17	0.52 × 0.40 × 0.19	0.41 × 0.37 × 0.16
μ (Mo Kα) (mm ⁻¹)	2.807	3.000	3.178	3.371
λ (Å)	0.71073	0.71073	0.71073	0.71073
Temperature (K)	293(2)	100	100	293
2θ _{max} (°)	56.54	56.6	56.6	56.6
Reflections collected	14953	5464	5066	9228
Independent	1986	1490	1430	1386
Reflections	(<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.0296)	(<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.061)	(<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.056)	(<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.037)
Reflections observed [<i>I</i> > 2.0 σ(<i>I</i>)]	1986	1162	1138	1187
Goodness-of-fit	1.050	0.86	0.87	0.76
<i>R</i> ; <i>R</i> _w	0.0223, 0.0628	0.0365, 0.0849	0.0336, 0.0799	0.0198, 0.0545
Largest difference peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	-0.905, 0.819	-1.44, 1.40	-0.90, 1.03	-0.54, 0.57

$$^aR = \Sigma (|F_o| - |F_c|) / \Sigma |F_o|; ^bWR = \{ \Sigma w(|F_o|^2 - |F_c|^2)^2 / \Sigma W(F_o^2)^2 \}^{1/2}$$

Conclusions :

The solvent-free condition for the synthesis of polydentate Schiff base ligand has been reported. By this method one can get even higher yield (~95% or more) compared to that of traditional methods (~85% or less) avoiding the use of toxic solvents which otherwise remains as a waste and pollutes the environment. All the lanthanide complexes were made through unique benign synthetic route. The IR spectra of **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** exhibits a very strong absorptions corresponding to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretches of **L** are located at the region of 1650 cm^{-1} . The UV-Visible spectra of these four complexes involve only the electronic transition within the $4f$ orbitals ($f-f$ transitions) which are forbidden by the Laporte-selection rule and the colour are not intense. For all the complexes experimentally found magnetic moment values are in good agreement with that of the calculated magnetic moments values for $\text{Ln}^{\text{III}}\text{L}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}, 4f^7; \text{Tb}, 4f^8; \text{Dy}, 4f^9; \text{Ho}, 4f^{10}$) as well as in good correlation with that of spectral results.

The lanthanide complexes are hepta coordinated and have distorted pentagonal bipyramidal geometry. The metal-N1 bond distances decreases steadily from Gd 2.747 Å to Ho 2.708 Å through Tb 2.731 Å and Dy 2.716 Å. This decrease in bond distance is due to lanthanide contraction. These types of lanthanide complexes are synthetically important and they have been synthesized by using aqueous ethanolic medium. The present methodologies are non-toxic and low cost pathway for synthesizing important inorganic compounds.

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. 618517, 618518, 618519 and 618520 for compounds **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** respectively. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www:http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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